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Content and Practical Significance of Educating Preschool Children on the Basis of National Values

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***Abstract:** This article discusses the content of educating preschool children in preschool institutions on the basis of national values and its social basis.*

***Keywords:** national values, cultural and historical heritage, spiritual upbringing, sense of patriotism, system of national values, preservation, brotherhood, spiritual closeness, past and spiritual heritage, a sense of homeland.*

INTRODUCTION

The interests and abilities of preschool children are manifested in the practical and theoretical interaction of educators with their students, taking into account spiritual resources and the requirements and needs of the present time. When educating preschool children on the basis of universal human values, it is necessary to understand their essence. Values are divided into several types according to their essence. In particular, a person and his life are considered the highest value. "It is absurd to talk about the value of something where there is no knowledge of a person." [Khasanova, 2015. 778].

Therefore, respecting the value of a person, improving his life, developing his knowledge and cultural level, preserving his health, and protecting his life are the main directions of our state policy. All the fundamental changes and reforms taking place in our society are aimed at ensuring that people's lives are full, rich, and beautiful, that a person feels truly free, that he is the owner of the results of his labor, his destiny, and his country.

The infinite number of things and phenomena surrounding a person, including those within national spirituality, that have special significance and value for a particular individual or social group, or a specific nation, or all of humanity, are called values. National values are the customs, traditions, qualities, morals and ethics, lifestyle, holidays, buildings, national clothes, household items, and

livelihoods of a particular people that are worthy of respect by the majority of this people. For example, the Uzbeks' hard work, hospitality, kindness and gentleness, enthusiasm and obedience, mutual understanding with people of different categories, forgiveness, thoughtful and thoughtful work, and peace-loving are considered Uzbek national values.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

We all know that the sustainable development and progress of each state depends on the human factor, in particular, on the scientific, creative and spiritual potential of the younger generation. Today, the problems of youth education are a common issue for almost all countries. On the topic of youth education, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev said at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly: "Today's youth is the largest generation in the history of mankind, as they number 2 billion people. The future and well-being of our planet depend on what kind of people our children will become. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to realize their potential, to prevent the spread of the "virus" of the idea of violence. For this, we believe that it is necessary to develop multilateral cooperation in the field of social support for the younger generation, protecting its rights and interests" [Sh. Mirziyoyev. 2017. 6]. The age-old traditions of the Uzbek people, including traditions in the field of education, are associated with the sacred religion of our ancestors. Greeting the elderly, Such traditions as being polite to neighbors have been instilled in Uzbek families, regardless of their religious affiliation, instilled in young people. Taking into account the important role of Islamic education in the upbringing of youth, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev put forward a number of ideas and initiatives in 2017-2018. In particular, the relevant resolutions of the Head of State and the Cabinet of Ministers on the establishment of the Imam Bukhari International Scientific Research Center in Samarkand region, the Imam Termizi Scientific Research Center in Termez, and the Center for Islamic Civilization in Uzbekistan in Tashkent were adopted [Sh.Mirziyoyev. 2019. No. PQ-4307]. In addition to studying the invaluable scientific and educational heritage of our great ancestors, the main task of these institutions is to educate young people to look at the great and glorious past with respect and pride, to become a generation worthy of their great ancestors, to seek knowledge and enlightenment.

RESULTS

The development of national forms of interests and abilities of preschool children is one of the important tasks set for preschool educational organizations. "The interests and abilities of preschool children are manifested in the practical and theoretical communication of educators with their children, taking into account spiritual sources and the requirements and needs of the present time" [Azizova, 2010. 3]. When educating preschool children on the basis of universal human values, it is necessary to understand its essence. In order to educate preschool children on the basis of national values, and to effectively instill national-spiritual, ethnic values in the minds of young people, it is necessary to work with scientists, writers, and poets on the topic of the harmony of nationality and national-spiritual values in preschool educational organizations.

It would be appropriate to show videos related to the life and creative path of preschool children. The organization of integrated spiritual and moral education of preschool children is a holistic pedagogical process aimed at a specific goal, in which the following pedagogical tasks are solved:

1. Preschool children are given information about the essence of spiritual and moral norms and moral relations and their significance in the life of society.

2. Creating a need for the acquisition of spiritual and moral concepts in preschool children, forming a spiritual and moral consciousness.
3. Forming positive spiritual and moral qualities in preschool children (patriotism, hard work, a sense of beauty, honesty, cleanliness, mutual friendship, harmony, eloquence, generosity, courage, etc.).
4. Formation of moral and spiritual behavior, character and will in preschool children.
5. Formation of moral and spiritual culture in preschool children.

In the implementation of these tasks, it is possible to identify the spiritual, educational and educational problems in preschool educational organizations, as well as the positive factors that serve the system of moral and spiritual education of preschool children in classes, as well as pedagogical problems in it.

In preschool educational organizations, the activities of our educators in helping our younger generations understand the interests of the people, nation and homeland, further enhance their glory, study and adequately evaluate science and culture, the rich heritage, history, religion and values of our ancestors are of great importance. In order to educate preschool children on the basis of national values, and to effectively instill national-spiritual and ethnic values in the minds of young people, it would be appropriate to show video films about the life and creative path of scientists, writers and poets on the topic of the harmony of nationality and national-spiritual values in preschool educational organizations.

DISCUSSION

Of course, each nation should not remain confined to its own national values. Studying the values of other nations has always been one of the factors of development. “No matter how close and influential the values are to each other, the main path and criterion of spiritual perfection for each nation remains national values” [Boboyeva, 2000. 105].

The good customs and rituals of a nation can take deep root in the life of a nation only when they correspond to the spirit of another nation, to its national spiritual needs and requirements. The thing or event that every nation values is, first of all, related to its national spirituality. National values are not an unchanging phenomenon. With the improvement of social, economic, and spiritual life associated with the development of the nation, and with changes in living and working conditions, national values are also created to develop. Educating children of preschool age on the basis of universal human values requires thinking based on the national idea, deep knowledge and specialization from the younger generation. Its basis is our national values. The feeling of living in a new way, building a free and prosperous homeland, a free and prosperous life, sets more responsible tasks for the younger generation than for the older generation. In particular, the fact that changes in consciousness and thinking, as well as spiritual values, lag behind the demands of life is associated with deficiencies in spiritual potential.

CONCLUSION

A new, systematic approach to national education, the study of psychological laws in the guaranteed formation of basic qualities in a child, requires the full development of the socio-pedagogical potential of the family, preschool education, general secondary, secondary specialized vocational, higher educational institutions, neighborhoods in this matter, and raising scientific and methodological cooperation and coherence between them to a new level.

The main goals and objectives of education and upbringing of preschool children are to develop children mentally and physically and prepare them for school, to ensure the development of their

psyche, personal abilities, aspirations and needs, taking into account national and universal values, regional characteristics, and to prepare them for school education. It is appropriate to raise preschool children on the basis of universal human values, to bring the opportunities of our blessed religion, and to use our great spiritual and educational heritage to the forefront in their educational and cultural education.

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